
Full Paper

**IOT-BASED DESIGN FOR PERSONAL ELECTRONIC HEALTH
MONITORING SYSTEM FOR NIGERIA PRIMARY CARE
(PEHMS)**

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ABSTRACT

This project is about a microcontroller-based Personal electronic health monitoring system used to monitor vital signs of a patient remotely. The vital signs include heart rate, temperature and Electrocardiogram (ECG) measurement. The system measures the variation in blood volume at the fingertip using optical sensors after every heartbeat, and a pair of probes to measure ECG and the temperature of the patient is measured using a temperature sensor. In this study, Visual Basic will be used to create real-time displays of signals picked up from the human body. Visual Basic is recommended because it can analyze data and show results in real time. This entails designing suitable sensors, correctly altering the circuitry, and ensuring real-time display. The research consists of three different channels for all three variables that the device will continually measure and display. Electrocardiogram, oxygen saturation, and body temperature are the three factors. Finally, it is simpler to use because a Windows-based GUI software built with Visual Basic is used to control some of the functions. The requirement for real-time vital sign display has guided the development of this study. Real-time output will be shown using Windows-based applications..

Keywords: vital signs, IOT, microcontroller, health, monitoring, sensor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Personal electronic health monitoring (PEHMS), commonly referred to as a vital signs monitor, is basically a real-time gadget that shows signals from the human body that have been received. While it is commonly utilized in medical institutes worldwide, it is not widely utilized in Nigeria and other nations with few resources. Medical professionals would benefit from the diagnosis and continued recording of real-time data by utilizing remote patient monitoring systems during routine activities for correct monitoring, treatment, and would increase illness management both at home and remotely.

The possibility of electronic personal health records has sparked a lot of interest because of inherent problems, which has inspired academics to create novel designs and implement complete patient monitoring solutions for use in homes and hospitals. Although current systems in hospitals permit continued monitoring of the vital signs of patients, these systems essentially confine patient to hospital bed because sensors must be hardwired to bedsides that are close to PCs or monitors. However, with the advancement of technology such as Wi-Fi and Bluetooth enables wireless patient monitoring thanks to advancements in the fields of electronics for microchips, networks and communication, integrated optics, and other associated technologies.

An electronic personal health record has no widely accepted definition. It's an "electronic application that enables people to access, manage, and share their health information—typically in a private, secure, and confidential environment." There are various models and variations in the extent to which the patient or a healthcare professional controls the patient's record and access rights, as well as the tools and interactions. There are simpler versions, some of which are computer- or web-based patient records that are patient-created, patient-stored, and patient-managed. As the name implies, an electronic personal health record is a type of system or technology created to monitor a health care setting for monitoring, diagnosis, treatment and prevention.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

According Choyon et al., (2020), a taxonomy of healthcare monitoring sensors is presented, as well as an investigation of wireless and wearable sensor-based IoT monitoring systems. They go into considerable detail about the challenges and

unresolved issues around security in healthcare systems, privacy, and QoS.

Rajesh Ranjan et al. (2004) created a method for configuring infrastructure health monitoring systems. With particular focus on the wireless transmission system's low-frequency response properties for Wifi. According to Pyper C. et al. (2004), the quantity and caliber of studies on electronic personal records are still scarce. However, the research that is already available indicates that patient-professional communication and trust are improving, as well as patient self-care confidence, compliance with chronic illness management, and record accuracy. It is important to note that patients enjoy online prescription reordering, results of tests, disease management strategies, trend charts, lists of medications and encrypted communications in particular, according to Claudia Pagliari et al. (2007). The policy working group on electronic sharing involving doctors and patients made this suggestion in its final report in 2020.

A wireless health monitoring prototype system is the main topic of Mahmud, S. et al.'s (2015) research, with a particular focus on measuring the electrical activity of the heart. He took into account trade-offs between power and communication range when deciding between two different wireless heart monitors for indoor and outdoor use. Integrated circuits and system design for sensor nodes, including analog and digital building blocks for RF data links, are presented by Hui (2007). He suggested performing part of the computations digitally in the sensor node before the results are sent to the rest of the system in order to reduce the power consumption of the sensor node. A wireless health monitoring system prototype that can transmit SMS on the health status of the patient is shown by Priya (2009). The project was divided in to three stages; data acquisition, data processing and communication.

A GSM device or SMS gateway is used by the monitoring system to automatically send the data as an SMS message to the doctor's mobile phone while also periodically updating the hospital database. A low power wireless acquisition module is presented by Figueiredo (2010) for use in applications like ambient assisted living and wearable health monitoring systems. The electrocardiogram (ECG), activity, and local temperature of the user are all continuously monitored by the acquisition module. The module is worn on the user's chest as due to of its fabrication from a flexible PCB, the complete absence of connecting wires, and the incorporation of flexible and

dry ECG monitoring electrodes on the data collection module, and these do not need to be prepared with electrolyte gel.

With the COVID-19 epidemic, it became abundantly evident that developing biomedical devices was the way forward. Personal electronic health monitoring is now possible thanks to recent developments in wireless communication, their widespread adoption, and the growth of IoT (internet of things) technology. According to Ana et al. (2013), remote monitoring makes it simple for medical staff to keep an eye on patients, no matter where they are. It is now possible to reference simple but life-saving diagnostic and treatment guides, tools to calculate pulse and respiration rate, and proper prescription dosages with the help of smartphone-based applications. When there are any modifications in a patient's health relative to standard values, the IoT system will notify a doctor or physician. (Bhardwaj et al., 2022).

According to Marwa et al., (2021), the goal of their study is to create a patient-centered home monitoring system that meets customers' individual needs and shifts medical treatment from the hospital right into the home. It creates a trustworthy system for managing care, cutting costs and preserving lives. In order to acquire important patient indicators like blood pressure, heart rate, ECG, glucometer, ventilation, and body temperature level, our model utilised a variety of biomedical sensing units. These observed data are essential for exploiting patient knowledge and comprehension to enhance healthcare through the introduced mobile application's supported user interfaces.

Rajeswari et al. (2021), Yüksel (2022) and Abdulmalek et al. (2022) reviewed that examines the latest recent advancements in IoT-enabled healthcare monitoring systems. The study investigates the benefits of IoT-based healthcare systems in terms of their importance and the advantages of IoT healthcare. They provided the most recent research on IoT-based healthcare monitoring systems based on a thorough analysis of the literature. The literature review contrasts various systems' efficacy, efficiency, data protection, privacy, security, and monitoring.

Based on the suggested foregoing, Imran et al. (2021) created a health monitoring system for senior individuals that may be used in their homes, ambulances, and hospitals. Through the use of biological sensors, the system recognizes deteriorating conditions and alerts the authorities for quicker interventions. Blood glucose levels, heart rate,

body position, and body temperature are all monitored via wearable biomedical sensors. The health sensing data was examined for irregularities using threshold and machine learning-based methods. Performance parameters for the proposed architecture are analyzed in terms of round trip time, dependability, job drop rate, and latency. Performance results demonstrate that the suggested architecture for monitoring the health of older patients can offer dependable answers for important problems in IoT environments.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Material, Methods and Design methodology

In the Present Design, microcontroller is the heart of the Entire Design. Each of the monitoring system has its own microcontroller that receives and output information to their respective output devices. For ease of construction, the materials used include printed circuit board, liquid crystal display, PIC microcontroller, Operational Amplifier, this makes the construction of individual section to be achieved. Software is also used in the construction, most of this software are written in both C and assembler language and it is combined together with the Hard Ware to achieve the desired result.

3.2 Methodology

A separate module is built and implemented for each task using a modular approach. The modules includes: Pulsed Oximeter, Thermometer, Electrocardiograph, and the system power supply. (See Figure 1)

This research describes a microcontroller based vital sign monitoring system that uses different type of sensor and control circuitry to obtain three basic health Vital Sign of a patient. The unit consists of an Electrocardiograph, pulse Oximeter and a thermometer circuit. Each of these units will be further broken down and discussed in full detail as shown below. (See Figure 1.1)

This circuit for the digital thermometer is shown in fig 2. It makes use of Dallas DS1820 Temperature sensor to detect the changes in the Human body temperature. The circuit for this electronic thermometer was made in such a way that the range is controllable over a certain range so that it would also be suitable for other applications. The measuring of a person's body temperature is one example of a potential use case. The control range can be varied in 0.25 °C steps from -25 °C to +75 °C.

Figure 1 Block Diagram for the Proposed Electronic Nurse

The Power Supply section

Figure 1.1 Circuit diagram for the power supply section

Schematic Diagram for the Digital Thermometer section

Figure 2 : complete circuit diagram for the Digital Thermometer

Figure 3 : complete circuit diagram for the pulse oximeter

- Easy programming
- Affordability of development tools

A Programmable Integrated Circuit (PIC) microcontroller and a few OpAmps with some sensors seemed to be the best choice for this purpose based on these criteria. The microcontrollers selected were PIC16F84A and PIC16F628A. These are 18 pin Enhanced Flash Microcontroller produced by Microchip.

4. DISCUSSION AND FURTHER WORK

4.1 Discussion

The Personal Electronic Health Monitoring PEHMS system offers an alternative to the traditional technique of taking a patient's vital signs. The device enables remote patient monitoring, which has many benefits for both patients and doctors. The pulse oximeter has been designed for use in determining the heart rate of a patient. The thermometer serves as a vital instrument in the measuring of Human body temperature. This unit is program to take input from an external factory calibrated sensor then convert the signal to a temperature equivalent from the signal that it input into the microcontroller. The Electrocardiograph unit measures the electrical Signal from the heart and then sends it to a PC for viewing and interpretation. This is made possible through the USB interface and the Graphical User Interface that interpret the signal into a meaningful trace. The unit also consists of a microcontroller that is programmed to communicate with PC.

To ensure the quality and functionality of all our software components, a clever microcontroller will be used to drive them (Onuora et al., 2020). A new era of personalized, wearable, and pervasive electronics health has begun.

4.2 Recommendations and Suggestions for further work

This recommendation is generalized and also based on the problems that emerge if this project is to be implemented. They are listed as follows.

1. To improve miniaturization of the project, surface-mount components should be incorporated alongside the targeted circuits on a printed circuit board with two sides and surface-mount components should be introduce in subsequent design.

2. In the future design, a microcontroller with higher memory capacity should be used to introduce flexible features and improve functionally of the project.

5 CONCLUSION

Reliable technology is required for patient health monitoring as healthcare technologies continue to improve outcomes and healthcare moves out of hospitals and into homes. Vital sign monitors give patients simple but crucial information about their physical health. Unfortunately, a lot of the current vital sign monitoring systems are prohibitively expensive and difficult to use. Most have sophisticated interfaces that do not fit in with the home setting and are created for hospital use. There is a need for more equipment that is made expressly for use at home by patients, their families, and caretakers.

The research's description of personal electronic health monitoring satisfies the necessity for an easily usable vital signs monitor for usage at home. The project is intended to track the three (3) vital signs of body temperature, blood oxygen saturation, and heart rate in order to provide comprehensive health care monitoring. The buttons and visible LCD panels address accessibility.

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